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Dr Cíntia Mara Ribas de Oliveira has been a full-time professor at Universidade Positivo (UP) since 2000 and a researcher at Centro de Pesquisa da Universidade Positivo (CPUP) since 2016. She served as the Assistant Coordinator of the Graduate Program in Environmental Management (2020-2023), where she teaches and supervises graduate students since the program's foundation in 2011. She has a bachelor's degree in chemistry and completed her Master and PhD in Biological Sciences – Biochemistry at Universidade Federal do Paraná (Brazil). She has been working on multi- and interdisciplinary projects in Environmental Science and Environmental Management, focused on environmental assessments based on monitoring strategies which integrate technological issues and social perspectives to understand anthropogenic impacts on ecosystems besides human health concerns.

ACTIONS OF THE CPUP/PPGAMB-UP GROUP IN THE BEESNESS PROJECT - BEHIND THE SWEET TASTE OF HONEY: PHYSICOCHEMICAL FINGERPRINTS OF HONEY FROM *Melipona mandacaia* FROM THE SÃO FRANCISCO VALLEY (BRAZIL)

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Abstract

Chemometrics has been used to highlight differences in the composition of similar products, expanding the analytical capabilities of characterisation techniques. Some of the applications of this approach have been reported for the identification of adulteration in products, geographic fingerprints or producing species¹. However, the combination of various analytical techniques and the application of chemometrics as a strategy for quality assurance of products with nutritional has not yet been fully explored. This strategy can be useful for products from unique, biodiverse biomes vulnerable to anthropogenic actions, as is the case of the Caatinga biome (Brazil). This work, within the scope of the BEESNESS project, brought together several research institutions

from both sides of the Atlantic (Brazil and Portugal) to contribute to the development of an analytical methodology for advanced physicochemical characterisation of honey produced by *Melipona mandacaia*, in areas with different anthropogenic pressure profiles in the Caatinga (São Francisco Valley). The samples collected in urban and natural areas were analysed using Raman spectroscopy, ¹H monodimensional NMR, and HSQC (¹H-¹³C) two-dimensional NMR, as well as differential scanning calorimetry (DSC). The data were treated and compared to commercial honey of *Apis mellifera*, and the results indicated the potential of the techniques to discriminate honey among areas and species. Physicochemical fingerprints were observed, and the results of the chemometric relationships will be integrated with other variables, like sampling site characteristics, anthropogenic pressure and biological responses of bees collected by the project. The herein methodological approach may give rise to a tool for valuing the ecosystem services provided by M.

mandacaiá in the Caatinga. Bridging the gaps between analytical techniques and integrated sets of socio-environmental management, nature conservancy may be achieved with a standing biome bioeconomy behind "the sweet taste of honey".

References

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